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SALIENT FEATURES OF A GOOD COMMERCIAL CONTRACT FOR AN EARTH MOVING INDUSTRY IN THE INDIAN CONTEXT

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ABSTRACT

This article emphasis on the very need of signing of commercial contract instead of mere signing of LOI. i.e. Letter Of Intent and what should be the Dos and Don'ts involved in shaping up the final terms and conditions of the said contract. This will protect interest of service provider to the large extent.

KEYWORDS:

Commercial Contract, Salient Features, Earth Moving Industries, the Dos and Don'ts

INTRODUCTION

Dear readers,

You have appreciated my earlier three papers published under various categories. This is the fourth one under the heading:

**“Important Features of a good commercial contract from the watch full eyes of a Credit Controller
Applicable for Earth Moving Industries in the Indian Context”**

Commercial Contract is a very strong tool to start the business with the new party. It is very much stronger than the LOI. i.e. Letter of Intent. It is always safe to sign a contract after signing LOI but many companies prefer to sign only LOI. But in case of failure of committed payment from the parties commercial contract framed with at most precaution and considering all Dos and Don'ts is a very good weapon in the hands of a company.

Looking at the experience rendered at the Managerial Capacity in various organisations and after that rendering my valuable suggestions to various corporates through my Consultancy Services for the past few years I have tried to collate all the major points of the a good contract as given below. Kindly note that these may vary from industry to industry and as per the requirement of clients and companies present at the time of signing of a contract.

Many companies give their equipment's like RMC, Tower Crane, Boom Placer, Stone crushing machines , Cutting and Bending Machines, passenger lifts fixed on site etc on hire basis. This is may be on per day basis, an hourly basis or monthly or till the end of a site building. But these companies end up of losing major chunk or profit margin at the end of contract because of not sufficiently covering each and every aspect while preparing the contract. The companies/agencies whose intentions are not to pay the debt of the service providers are taking advantages of these loopholes and succeed in looting the rightful money they owe to the service providers. At the end service providers are compelled to do one time settlement and lose major chunk of profit in this process. These companies also end up waiting longer period to give justice by the court of land.

Format of contents of contract which will be signed by both the parties at the time of supplying and hiring the earth moving instruments.

- 1) Check whether purchase order number and date has been mentioned in the beginning of the contract by the **hirer** of the machine
- 2) Check whether the work order is addressed to the right authority and registered address of the **hirer** of the machine
- 3) If the work order is issued after earlier issue of LOI then please check the number of the said LOI is mentioned in this contract
- 4) Check whether scope of work has been mentioned while start of the contract with mentioned of unit/period and rate. The rate is per equipment per day basis.
- 5) Check whether rate is covering day to day shift basis work and also over time (if any) by the operators who are running these equipment.
- 6) Check whether period of contract is mentioned on the contract correctly. For IT department, they should immediately fix alerts on the system one month before end of the contract. This will trigger alert to the sales manager, head of sales department, operations manager and head of operations, credit controller and accounts head to take suitable action in this regard.
- 7) Check rate is giving inclusive of what? Means whether it includes cost of men, power, machines, spares, lubricants, oils and greases, maintenance of machine or parts thereof.
- 8) Check whether standard per litre diesel consumption average has been mentioned in case of transit mixtures and for drum separately.
- 9) Check if the transit mixtures are not giving specified average at the site, then whether the penalty clause to the supplier of the machines has been mentioned on the contract.
- 10) Check whether proper rate of deduction of Tax Deducted at source (TDS in India) is mentioned on the contract. For this supplier of the machines has to provide PAN and service tax registration numbers, copies of certificates to the hirer of the machines. They will deduct appropriate TDS while paying rent and other charges to the supplier of the machines from time to time.
- 11) Check whether the hirer of the machines has also accepted the duties like service (In India) tax also while accepting the terms of contract.
- 12) Many a times rate is quoted inclusive of all rates (just to make it competitive) and win the contract. But if the person/staff entering the contract is not aware of the same or have not gone through the contract thoroughly, then he may enter basic rates + applicable taxes/duties on the system. This will create billing disputes with each other and delay the payments. Credit controller is dragged in this eventually to recover the money before the bills turns into old.
- 13) Check whether supplier of the machines is abiding by all the Labour Laws, other statutory obligations and WCP (work man compensation policy in India) of land. The supplier should give all the documentary evidence to the hirer of the machines that he is authorized to deploy labour for the purpose.
- 14) Check whether all the equipment's are properly insure before hirer starts deploying the sate on site.
- 15) Please reject any machines which is being deployed without adherence the clause number 14 and 13 to avoid any future difficulties or litigations.
- 16) Check whether cost of mobilization of equipment is bare by whom. Generally if the contract period is less than six months then the hirer of the machines bares the same. If the contract period is more than six months then the supplier of the machines bares the same.
- 17) For this point IT department should fix alerts while entering the contract. Bill of mobilization is to be generated automatically keeping in view the above mentioned point.
- 18) Check where supplier of the machines is adhering to the safety standards set by the industry. Get this point checked properly by the engineering department thoroughly.
- 19) Check whether hirer of the machines is ready to give food, stay, water and power to the operators deployed on the site. Sometimes hirer of the machines do the same on chargeable basis or sometimes it is free of cost.
- 20) Check whether the operators deployed on the site by the supplier of the machines are up to the standard fixed and accepted by the industry norms. Check their driving license for the purpose.
- 21) Check the billing period and terms and conditions mentioned on the contract by the hirer of the machines. Sometimes the billing starts from the day the machines arrived on the sites. Sometimes the billing starts once the machines get started.

- 22) I have seen many a times that the person/staff entering the contract on the system makes mistakes in this. This leads to wrong generation of bills, billing disputes, delay in payments, un necessary raising of questions or fingers on each one. Credit controller has to handle this situation diplomatically; train the staff to avoid such mistakes, balance the situation and recover the money before the bills gets aged.
- 23) Check whether there is proper system in place by the hirer of the machines to keep track of daily work done by the operator inter alia machine. Normally Log Sheet is provided to each operator for each machine. He enters daily work done during the day and at the end of the day the same is counter signed by the supervising authority of the hirer of the machine.
- 24) **This Log Sheet is the Bible for the service provider. All the billing disputes has to solved within the preview of the data recorded on the Log Sheet.**
- 25) Check where proper maintenance clause for the machines supplied has been incorporated by the supplier of the machine. Check whether the machines are maintained properly as per the norms set. If not done or ignored this will lead to any accident and halt the project work.
- 26) Check whether possible losses which may arrive at the because of the point number 25 has been incorporated by the hirer of the machines. Check whether the same has been negotiated and accepted by the supplier of the machines.
- 27) Check whether hirer has admitted to pay security deposit to the supplier of the machine. Normally the sum is equivalent to the one month rental. Check whether the said clause has been added by the supplier in the contract.
- 28) Check whether hirer has added clause of breakdown of machine in the contract, if the machine is break down for more than 24 hours then the supplier should replace the same with the new one. If not supplier will pay charges to the hirer as agreed mutually as per the terms of contract
- 29) Check whether clause of indemnity against all the liability, losses, charges and expenses including third party has been added by the supplier in the contract.
- 30) Check whether hirer has mentioned the clause of termination and the same is agreed by the supplier as per the terms of contract
- 31) Check whether the clause of arbitration is mentioned in the works contract by both the parties and the said is not objectionable to either parties.
- 32) Check whether hirer has mentioned the clause of jurisdiction in the case of any disputes arising of the currency of the said contract
- 33) Check whether both the competent authorities from both the sides has signed and sealed the contract

Some additional points from Legal Point of View

Check points from legal point of view which will help the supplier of the machines to safe guard the interest of his money entirely.

- 1) Please collect registered address of the client
- 2) Please collect incorporation certificate of the client
- 3) Please collect PAN (permanent account number) and residential address of the directors
- 4) Please develop system to get notice of any change of address by the hirer of the machine
- 5) Please develop system to get known any change in the authorized signatory of the hirer of the machine
- 6) Please develop system through which all the proof of dispatch of each bill will be collected, scanned and preserved in good manner. Needless to emphasise the importance of the same.
- 7) Please develop system through which supplier of the machine will get commissioning report of each report. This will help accounts department to generate bill correctly.
- 8) Please develop system through which every single log sheet of each machine is preserved in a good manner. This is only document through which supplier can prove them correct and demand law full money from the hirer of the machine.
- 9) Please develop system through which every single letter of extension of contract of machine is collected from the hirer of the machine with out fail
- 10) Please develop system through which majority of the terms and conditions are standardized to avoid any avoidance of any point in future.

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This list may not be covering all the aspects but still many important aspects of a good commercial contract for the Earth Moving Companies. Kindly feel free to contact the undersigned with your valuable suggestions to make this article complete in all sense.

Thanking you.

Yours Trully,

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